

EOSC Support Office Austria: Visions, needs and requirements for research data and practices

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In 2015 the vision of a federated system of infrastructures supporting research by providing an open multi-disciplinary environment to publish, find and re-use data, tools and services led to the launch of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC). Against this background, bodies such as the [EOSC Association](#) on the European level and the [EOSC Support Office Austria](#) on the national one have been established.

Within this framework and since research has always been at the heart of EOSC, we are eliciting visions, needs and requirements for research data and practices from researchers who are located at public universities in Austria. Let's see what Let's see what Computer Scientist Fajar J. Ekaputra has to say!

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MC: Please, may you explain what your research focuses on?

FJE: My general topic is about semantic web technologies and their application in various domains, including, for example, Industry 4.0, the environmental domain, smart cities, and smart energy systems. Recently, I've also been involved in research related to the neuro-symbolic AI system, which is a combination of symbolic AI, such as knowledge graphs and logics, and sub-symbolic AI systems, which basically represents Machine Learning. My focus is on knowledge graphs and how they help with standard Machine Learning as well as how Machine Learning can improve developments of semantic web artifacts.

MC: What data are you working with?

FJE: It really depends on the project. However, we also do get data from industrial partners. For example, we once got data generated by an e-car charging station over time. We thus had data for

every second or milliseconds even - depending on the sensor granularity. The type of data we are usually working with is structured data which can be numeric or text.

MC: So how do you define, collect, reprocess, analyze, interpret, and store data?

FJE: Again, it depends on the exact project or rather Use Case. However, the first step usually is to clean the data by either using a programmatic approach, such as python script to remove anomalies, or manually with tools such as Excel. I then typically process the data and create a knowledge graph, which basically means that I create an RDF (Resource Description Framework) representation of a specific dataset.

MC: Please, may you explain what an RDF is?

FJE: Sure! An RDF is a W3C recommendation for representing web data. It's open representation standard for knowledge graph. You can use

knowledge graphs as a knowledge base. It is, however, not like a typical relational database where you have columns and rows. It rather is a graph-structured data model that is used to represent and operate on data. There are nodes and edges. Edges connect nodes. Nodes can represent any objects, places, or persons. Edges are the relations connecting objects, places, or persons. For example, you and I could be represented as a node. We would be related via an edge called a colleague. Each of us also gets attributes defining us such as name, age, or sex. We can be related to another person, to a place, or to an object being defined by specific attributes of their own and so forth.

MC: Thanks for this very clear explanation. So what tools, software, services do you use and for what?

FJE: I usually work with semantic web tools such as Protégé, GraphDB, or Ontotext Refine. Sometimes, it is not enough, which is when I make a custom software application to do the processing by using either Java, or Python.

MC: Thank you. Earlier you mentioned that you do get data from industry partners – i.e. data that you have neither collected, nor generated yourself. Against this background, I would like to discuss issues with respect to trust in data quality. It is a very broad question, but how do you know that data are, or remain in high quality?

FJE: There are two things to be mentioned. First, in most cases, I have access to the gold standard data as a reference as well as experts that can help. Quality checks are also very useful, but I doubt that experts are always available to check datasets. We can, however, devise mechanisms that allow them to provide feedback every now and then. We can then use that as a control reference.

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Documenting the original goals of data generation as it helps to ensure that datasets are not taken out of context and used for things that simply do not align with them at all.

MC: What constitutes the quality of high-quality research data in your discipline, or rather what practices ensure quality in data?

FJE: There are several things that we can do. First, we work with a standard – SHACL, which is a W3C recommendation for validating or describing data constraints. We use it for checking the quality of the data being added to our systems.

Second, our community is building what is called an *Ontology Design and Patterns Repository*, where you can view the best practices in creating a data schema.

Third, we do have a Pitfall Scanner. There is a tool called OOPS, where you can upload your data model, and it will tell you if it finds defects in your modeling. Suggestions on what to do if there are included.

MC: When and why do you trust the quality of your research data, and when don't you?

FJE: Apart from the quality checks that I can do, I will never trust data quality 100%. After having checked the quality, however, I have more confidence to say that the quality is better at least.

MC: How do you judge the quality of research data of others, other disciplines, or rather, what are the criteria by which you judge it?

“I have learned that each discipline has their own quality criteria. Thus, there are many different perspectives on what constitutes a high-quality data set, or how to evaluate it. Despite this, correct metadata is relevant across disciplines to make sense of the data you intend to work with. Trusted experts can also help to see whether the data is of good quality.”

FJE: Over the years, I have learned that each discipline has their own quality criteria. Thus, there are many different perspectives on what constitutes a high-quality data set, or how to evaluate it. Despite this, correct metadata is relevant across disciplines to make sense of the data you intend to work with. Trusted experts can also help to see whether the data is of good quality.

MC: When and why do you trust the quality of research data collected and shared by others?

FJE: It depends on many factors such as the reputation of the data originator, or the reputation of the hosting platform, where the data is being collected, the completeness of the metadata. The latter includes the name of the originator, when a data set was created and therefore its age, the sources from which it has been collected, how the data was obtained, etc. The feedback from other users is also a criterion.

MC: Thank you very much.

Dr. Fajar J. Ekaputra is a Tenure Track Assistant Professor at the Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU Wien), Austria, specializing in Semantic Web, Knowledge Graphs Engineering, and their interaction with Machine Learning approaches. With a Ph.D. in Informatics from TU Wien and a strong background in engineering from Institut Teknologi Bandung, Indonesia, he focuses on developing reliable, effective data solutions for diverse applications, including auditing Hybrid AI systems and ensuring consistency in Cyber-Physical Systems. His contributions span foundational research and practical implementations, such as tools for AutomationML and ontologies for hydro power systems. Leading innovative projects like SLOGERT (log-based Knowledge Graphs) and AuditBox (AI audit trace management). Fajar has co-authored more than 70 peer-reviewed papers in various venues, earning recognition with best paper awards. He is active in international research communities, contributing to conferences like ISWC and ESWC as both organizer and committee member.